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Risk factors associated with wound dehiscence

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Abstract:

Background: The incidence of wound dehiscence continues to be around 0.3-10% despite the progress in the preoperative care during the last few decades. Wound dehiscence after abdominal surgery continues to be a challenging problem, which considerably prolongs hospital stay and is associated with significant mortality rate. The aim of this paper is to study the various risk factors that lead to wound dehiscence and the method to minimize it.

Patients and Methods: During 3 years period from April 1996 to April 1999 thirty patients (17 males and 13 females) developed wound dehiscence of all abdominal wall layers after abdominal surgery at Al-Kadhymiyia Teaching Hospital. Their age ranged from 2 months to 90 years. The patients who did not have a disruption of all layers of the abdominal wall were excluded from the study. The cases were studied to identify the preoperative, operative, and postoperative risk factors, related to wound dehiscence. The results of the patients were compared with control group (30 patients, of similar sex, age, and operative indication who had operation during the same period).

Results: Wound dehiscence occurred on average 8 days postoperatively (range 3-14). The primary diagnosis in both groups included malignancy (biliary, pancreatic, and urinary), acute abdomen (intestinal obstruction, acute appendicitis, intestinal perforation, acute pancreatitis, mesenteric vascular ischemia), obstructive uropathy, biliary disorders, and miscellaneous disorders (liver rupture, colonic ileus, pelvic abscess). The main preoperative risk factors associated with wound dehiscence were Hypoproteineimnia, anemia, and chronic lung disorders, while emergency surgical procedure was the main operative risk factor. The number of patients in the dehiscence group increased significantly when the number of risk factors increased.

Key words: Wound dehiscence-Risk factors-Abdominal surgery.

Introduction:

The incidence of wound dehiscence (The post operative separation of the abdominal musculoaponeurotic layers, which occurs within days and require intervention during the same hospital

stay) continues to be around 0.3-10% in various reports despite progress made in preoperative care during the last few decades. Wound dehiscence after abdominal surgery continues to be a challenging problem, which considerably prolongs hospital stay and is associated with mortality rate of 36% in 20 reviews of wound dehiscence published before 1940, and 18% in a review of 34 studies from 1950 to 1984 and dehiscence associated mortality rate does not appear to be declining [1,2,3,4,5,6]. The aim of this paper is to study the various risk factors associated with wound dehiscence and the methods to minimize.

Patients and Methods

During 3 years period from April 1996 to April 1999 thirty patients (17 males and 13 females) developed wound dehiscence of all abdominal wall layers after abdominal surgery at Al-Kadhymiyia Teaching Hospital. Their age ranged from 2 months to 90 years. The patients who did not have a disruption of all layers of the abdominal wall were excluded from the study. The cases were studied to identify the preoperative, operative, and postoperative risk factors, related to wound dehiscence. The cases were analyzed with complete review of the hospital stay, laboratory results, operative notes and bacteriological culture results. The patients nutritional status on admission was determined, the patients were considered malnourished if they had serum albumin level of < 35 g/l and weight loss of > 5 kg during the past 6 months. Obesity was defined as a body mass index (BMI) > 27 kg/square meter. Jaundiced patients had a serum bilirubin level > 50 mmol/l (normal 2-20 mmol/l)

and clinical jaundice. Anemia was defined as a hemoglobin value of < 11 g/l. The presence of peritonitis was confirmed by clinical examination and purulent exudates of the abdomen. Systemic infection was diagnosed by fever and rigor. Local wound infection was considered to be present if there was clinical signs of infection and positive bacteriological examination [6]. The preoperative risk factors, the underlying diseases, the factors which increase intra abdominal pressure postoperatively and post operative mortality were recorded. The information obtained from records and by direct contact with the patients. The results of the patients were compared with control group (30 patients, of similar sex, age, and operative indication who had operation during the same period. The statistical significance of these variables were determined using chi square analysis (contingency table method), Fisher exact test, and standard t test. The 95% confidence interval (CI) was used to assess the significance of the difference between the groups < 0.5 was considered significance.

Results:

Wound dehiscence occurred on average of 8 days postoperatively (range 3-14). The primary diagnosis in both groups included malignancy (biliary, pancreatic, and urinary), acute abdomen (intestinal obstruction, acute appendicitis, intestinal perforation, acute pancreatitis, mesenteric vascular ischemia), obstructive uropathy, biliary disorders, and miscellaneous disorders (liver rupture, colonic ileus, pelvic abscess). Table (1) shows the distribution of the primary diagnosis in both groups.

Table (1): shows the distribution of the primary diagnosis in both groups. Dehiscence Group (DG), Control group(CG).

Primary diagnosis	DG	CG
Malignancy(biliary, pancreatic, and urinary)	5	2
Acute abdomen (intestinal obstruction, acute appendicitis, intestinal perforation, acute pancreatitis, mesenteric vascular ischemia)	11	10
Obstructive uropathy	5	4
Miscellaneous disorders(liver rupture, colonic ileus,pelvic abscess)	4	6
Biliary disorders	5	8

All 30 dehiscence are treated surgically and the ruptured anterior abdominal wall fascia was closed with either absorbable suture continuously in 18 patients or interruptedly in 12 patients using additional non absorbable nylon suture in 30 patients, polyglycolic acid in 11 patients polyglactin in 19 patients for facial reclosure.

Three patients died (10%) within 30 days in our hospital two of them due to renal failure ,the third one due to cardiac stand still and another 3 patients (10%) died within 90 days after discharge, and their exact cause of death couldn't be determined.

Preoperative risk factors: There were 15 patients (50%) with preoperative hypoalbuminemia in the dehiscence group compared with only 10 patients (30%) in the control group (table 2) and this was significantly different (p=0.0005).Anemia was recorded in 8

out of 30 patients (26%)in the dehiscence group and 4 out of 30 patients (13.2%) in the control group(p=0.0035).Patients considered to be malnourished prior to surgery were more common in the dehiscence group 5 out of 30 (16.1%) than the control group 3out of 30 (10%); p=0.0316, as were also the patients chronic lung disease 12 out of 30 (40%)verses 4 out of 30(13.2%),respectively(p=0.026).

Operative risk factors: Patients undergoing emergency operative procedure were more common in dehiscence group 22 out of 30 (70%) than in control group (10 out of 30 (30%));(p=0.0423). In the dehiscence group ,18 patients underwent continuous closure (polyglycolic 14 ,polyglactin 4 and 12 interrupted closures (polyglycolic 10,ppolyglactin 2) of the anterior abdominal wall where as in the control group ,the anterior fascias of 14 patients were closed with continuous sutures (polyglycolic 12 ,polyglactin 2) and that of 16 patients with interrupted sutures (polyglycolic 14,polyglactin 2)no significant difference found.

The number of patients in the dehiscence group increased significantly when the number of risk factors increased from 0 to 5 (p=0.0001(Figure).In patients with 4 or 5 risk factors (8 out 11) and (11 out of 12), respectively, developed wound dehiscence. When the patients had 3,2,1, or 0 risk factors ,(5 out of 9),(3 out of 12),(2 out of 13),and (1 out 3)had wound disruption respectively.

Postoperative risk factors that increase intra abdominal pressure were present significantly more often in the dehiscence group.

The mean hospital stay in the dehiscence group was (25+₁₀ days), which was significantly longer than control group (11+₅ days; p=0.0001).The 30 days mortality rate in the dehiscence and control group was (10%) and (0%), respectively and 90 days mortality rate was (10%) and (3.3%) respectively.

dehiscence =0.7% versus 1.5%, respectively [7].

Table (2):Distribution of risk Factors between the two groups

Preoperative risk factors	DG	CG
Hypoalbuminemia	15 (50%)	10 (30%)
Chronic lung disease	12 (40%)	4 (13.2%)
Anemia	8 (26%)	4 (13.2%)
Diabetes Mellitus	6	7
Jaundice	6	5
Malnutrition	5	3
Obesity	3	4
Use of steroids	2	0
Operative risk factors		
Emergency surgery	22 (70%)	10 (30%)
Sepsis	14	10
Closure in layers		
Continuous	18	14
Interrupted	12	16

Discussion

In this study, no significant difference Could be demonstrated between the use of different types of sutures material Separate closure of the abdominal layers at the primary surgery did not influence the rate of wound dehiscence significantly. This result agrees with the result of Pollock study of randomized trial of mass versus layered closure, in 282 incisions found no difference in

Figure (1) Number of patients at risk

Wound dehiscence is more likely to occur in elderly patients than in younger age group, this is may be due to wound disruption occurred with less force [8].The male to female ratio in this study is similar to previous reports1.2:1.0. [9]. Malignancy is also a significant prognostic factor which agrees with other studies [10,11, 12], this is due to cancer induced cachexia. Hypoproteineimia and malnourished patients showed a preponderance of wound dehiscence, a finding that suggests Hypoproteineimia is a very strong risk factor, which similar to Makola study [13] and this is probably due to limited supply of aminoacid required for synthesis of collagen. Emergency surgery, showed a preponderance of wound dehiscence, which quite similar to other studies like Makola study [13,14].Chronic lung

disease and postoperative pulmonary complication are important systemic factors that may increase intra abdominal pressure through coughing during the early postoperative period [15].

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References:

- 1-Bruce A, wound dehiscence .Surgery clinic of North America 1997; 77:529-530.
- 2-Bowen A, Postoperative wound disruption and evisceration:An analysis of thirty-four cases with review of the literature .Am J Surg 1990; 47:3.
- 3-Poole GV.Mechanical factors in abdominal wound closure: the prevention of facial dehiscence .Surgery 1985; 97:631-639.
- 4-Madsen G,Fischer L,Wara P .Burst abdomen: clinical features and factors influencing mortality .Dan Bull 1992;39:183.
- 5-Greenberg AG,Saik RPM,Peskin GW. Wound dehiscence :pathophysiology and prevention .Arch Surg 1979;114:143.
- 6-Arnaud JP,Humbert W,Eloy MR,etal:Effect of obstructive jaundice on wound healing .Am J Surg 1981;141:593.
- 7-Pollock AV,Greenal MJ ,Evans M.Singlelayer mass closure of major laparotomies by continuous suturing .J Rsoc Med 1979;7:889.
- 8-Kenkin TP.The Burst abdominal wound:

mechanical approach Br J Surg 63:873 876,1976.

9-Larsen PN ,Nielsen K,Schulz A ,etal. Closure of the abdominal fascia after clean contaminated laparotomy .Acta Chir Scand 1989; 115:461-464.

10-Rubio PA ,Closure of abdominal wound ,with continuous non absorbable experience in 1,694 cases .Int Surg 1991; 76:159-160.

11-Thompson WD,Ravidan IS ,FrankIL:effect of Hypoprotiemia on wound disruption. Arch Surg 193836:500.

12-Lawrence WT,Norton JA,Harvey AK,etal:wound healing in sarcoma –bearing rats :tumor effects on cutaneous and deep wounds.J.Surg Oncol 1987;35:7.

13- Makola JT, Riviniemi,Juvonen T ,et al .Factors influencing wound dehiscence after midline laparotomies .Am j Surg 1995;170:387 .

14-Goodson WH III,Lindenfield SM,O.H.machi RS,et al:Chronic ureamia causes poor wound healing .Surg Forum1982;33:54.

15-Hogstrom H,Hagland U.Postoperative decrease in suture holding capacity in laparotomy wound and anesthesia .Acta Chir Scand 1985; 151:533-535